

A Study on Dietary Services in Public Hospitals of Sri Lanka: Reducing Food Waste and Enhancing Patient Outcomes

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ABSTRACT: Dietary services in public hospitals are integral to patient recovery and overall care. The existing dietary circular governing these services requires revision to enhance efficiency, effectiveness, and patient satisfaction while addressing cost concerns. A cross-sectional observational study was conducted using a mixed-method approach to identify gaps and inefficiencies in the current dietary practices, including focus group discussions, key informant interviews, and desk reviews. The findings indicated significant food waste in hospitals and considerable patient dissatisfaction with current dietary options. These challenges underscore serious gaps in aligning dietary practices with patient needs and resource allocation. This study emphasizes the importance of revising the dietary circular to establish more efficient and patient-centered dietary services. Proposed revisions focus on reducing food waste, improving the nutritional adequacy of meals, and addressing patient preferences, ultimately contributing to better clinical outcomes. The recommendations focus on developing a cost-effective strategy for hospital dietary services to achieve sustainable improvements that align with healthcare objectives. Updating and implementing these guidelines can greatly benefit the healthcare system by optimizing resource allocation and enhancing patient care in Sri Lankan public hospitals.

KEYWORDS: Dietary guideline Food waste, Hospital diet.

INTRODUCTION

Efficient hospital dietary services are essential for patient care, ensuring nutritional needs are met while minimizing food waste. Sri Lanka offers free healthcare services, including dietary assistance, to the public at the point of delivery. This provides significant advantages for both the patient and their family. Furthermore, hospital meals are considered an essential part of therapy, and every effort must be made to provide patients with fresh, appetizing, and nutritious meals (1). However, studies in Sri Lanka have revealed significant inefficiencies, including high levels of plate waste, outdated processes, and limited input from healthcare professionals in menu planning. These gaps affect patient satisfaction, increase costs, and contribute to environmental concerns (2)(3). Evidence from regional and international studies emphasizes the importance of improving food quality, service delivery, and monitoring systems to address these issues effectively. To enhance food intake and minimize food waste, active monitoring of patients' nutritional needs is recommended (1).

Justifications

Significant inefficiencies exist in hospital dietary services in Sri Lanka, with high levels of food waste attributed to outdated processes, inadequate menu planning, and insufficient medical professional involvement. Implementing mechanisms like "order on demand" has demonstrated the potential to reduce waste and enhance service efficiency.

Globally, research highlights the importance of factors such as food quality, temperature, timely service, and staff training in improving patient satisfaction and minimizing waste. Food waste is particularly concerning in specific hospital wards, such as paediatric units, where targeted guidelines are essential. Additionally, establishing robust monitoring and evaluation systems is crucial for ensuring continuous improvements in dietary service delivery.

These findings justify the need for a comprehensive revision of the existing dietary circular to address these issues and create a more efficient and patient-centered approach.

Objective

To study the dietary services in Public Hospitals of Sri Lanka.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In 2016, an interventional study conducted at the National Hospital of Sri Lanka (NHSL) highlighted the potential for reducing food wastage by improving the diet ordering format and incorporating the "order on demand" mechanism (4). Another study in Sri Lanka in DGH Warakapola revealed that plate waste in hospitals was as high as 24.26%. The entire process was heavily paper-based, involving setting menus, estimating diet requirements, and serving diets to patients. Menus were more focused on quantity rather than quality, with limited input from doctors and nurses in planning. Gaps in diet service processes, such as estimation errors, timeliness, and poor food appearance, contributed to reduced patient satisfaction and plate waste (2). A study done in Teaching Hospital Karapitiya found that the average per-patient and staff diet cost at TH Karapitiya is LKR 182.76, higher than the costs reported in similar studies from 2016 (LKR 119) (4) and 2022 (LKR 127) (3) in Sri Lankan government hospitals. This increase likely reflects inflation and improvements in diet quality over time. However, direct comparison is challenging due to differences in hospital types and study periods. Notably, this study included diet clerks' wages 50% of total kitchen staff salaries as part of the kitchen cost centre, unlike the previous studies (5). In a project conducted at District General Hospital (DGH) Chilaw, reorientation of the kitchen improved staff productivity, while food distribution by trained staff using client-friendly trolleys and plates enhanced service efficiency. Nutritional awareness among clients was supported through leaflets, leading to higher satisfaction with the food distribution system. These measures contributed to reducing food wastage, demonstrating a successful model of integrating operational improvements with client education to achieve sustainable outcomes (6).

In a study done in Malaysia, TAMBY Chik et al. (2019) identified the temperature and taste of food as the strongest dimensions influencing plate waste generation (7). A systematic review conducted (8) emphasized the importance of changing service systems, such as menus, serving times, patient needs, staff training, communication, and meal quality. Structural systems for ordering, production, and delivery also require evaluation and control mechanisms. Another review (9) underscored the need for structured systems to enhance training, competence, and teamwork in food service management.

In another article, food waste has been linked to several critical factors, including nutrient intake, menu performance, food acceptability, costs, and environmental impacts. Food waste values are particularly high in Paediatric wards, where institutions are often unaware of the magnitude of food waste produced. Given the scale of the problem, it is essential to implement effective measures to address food waste in healthcare settings (10). Globally, contributing factors to hospital food waste include food quality and quantity, patient satisfaction, patient characteristics, clinical conditions, meal times, and external food sources. The hospital environment also plays a significant role in influencing food waste generation. Strategies to monitor and improve hospital food services can significantly enhance food intake and reduce waste.

METHODOLOGY

Key Informant Interviews (KII) and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) - With relevant Ministry of Health Officials, Hospital Directors, Consultant Nutrition Physicians, Matrons/ Sisters, Administrative Officers, Accountants and Dietitians were conducted. Desk reviews. The existing dietary circular, and the expenditure on food and beverages in the line ministry hospitals and at the Provincial level hospitals were examined.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

The Key Informant Interviews and the Focus Group Discussions reveal the following. Matrons and dietitians emphasized that prepared food is wasted due to poor coordination in meal planning, wrong meal distribution time schedules, overestimating patient numbers, and a lack of patient preference in menu preparation. The hospital directors emphasized the need to revise the dietary guidelines regarding preparation and meal distribution schedules. Another group of stakeholders mentions the need to revise the food or menu preparation by emphasizing amending the substitutes for different types of food items. Some respondents noted that current dietary practices overlook regional and cultural adaptations in food selection, which should be addressed. It was also noted that structural changes and modifications to the infrastructure in the hospital kitchen area are recommended. Additionally, a matron from a tertiary hospital stated, "When patients receive food from home, the food waste increases."

Another respondent mentioned the lack of training of the hospital kitchen staff in meal preparation also leads to food wastage. “The meals are prepared by untrained junior staff most of the time, they should get a better training to prepare the food in a more palatable manner”. Some respondents expressed concerns about the limited efforts to gather patient feedback on meals, urging the hospital administration to improve this practice.

The desk review concentrated on the current dietary circular. It revealed that, besides the meal distribution times, the meal ordering process and menu preparation require revision and updates. This should involve relevant stakeholders, including medical professionals, hospital administrators, nursing officers, administrative officers, accountants, and dietitians.

DISCUSSION

One of the main findings of the study was that improper meal scheduling and distribution times in hospitals contributed to an increase in plate waste. These timing issues affected both the temperature and taste of the food. An article notes that temperature and taste are the most significant factors influencing the generation of plate waste. (7). Improvement in meal presentation has been shown to positively influence patients' visual perception as well as their perception of taste and smell. This enhancement leads to a significant reduction in food waste (1). The conducted interviews and FGDs revealed that improving food presentation is essential for increasing its acceptability among patients, thereby further reducing food waste.

The findings of the study revealed that the main proposed intervention is the revision of the existing dietary circular. Updating the circular with relevant stakeholders to include evidence-based practices such as "order on demand" mechanisms. Guidelines should be aimed at quality-focused menu planning and timely service and to strengthen systems for monitoring and evaluation to ensure continuous improvements. Further, it was revealed that enhancing staff training and teamwork by conducting regular training programmes for hospital staff on food service protocols, nutrition standards, and patient-centered care are vital steps in enhancing hospital dietary services. Similarly, an article discusses various aspects of flexible delivery systems, particularly regarding meal ordering near the time of consumption. It emphasizes the importance of involving patients in the provision of their food and meals. This approach requires active participation from patients and empowers them, aligning with the principles of patient-centered care (9).

To improve dietary services and reduce waste, it is proposed to establish feedback mechanisms and create platforms where patients, doctors, and nurses can provide input on menu planning and service quality. This will help ensure that services better align with patient needs. A study indicates that feedback is often seen as a problem not only from the patients' perspective but also from other stakeholders. It highlights the need for more transparent communication and suggests that regular meetings should be held with representatives at the operational level (11). Additionally, developing targeted guidelines for high-waste wards is recommended. This includes creating specialized interventions for the wards with high food waste, such as paediatric wards, with a focus on portion control and accommodating patient preferences.

CONCLUSION

Improving hospital dietary services is critical to reducing food waste, enhancing patient satisfaction, and promoting sustainable practices in Sri Lanka's healthcare system. By addressing inefficiencies through evidence-based interventions, such as revising the dietary circular, implementing modern technologies, and strengthening staff training, hospitals can significantly enhance service delivery. When revising the dietary guidelines, it is important to consider changes in menu planning, meal scheduling, the nutritional value of meals, and the quality and taste of the food served to patients. These measures will not only ensure better nutritional care for patients but also contribute to cost savings and environmental sustainability, creating a more effective and resilient healthcare system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Revising the existing dietary guidelines with the relevant stakeholders and staff training on food preparation and distribution are recommended in order to enhance hospital dietary services in public hospitals.

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